

datacamp

A
Technical Documentation
on
Predicting the Price of Used Cars
Using
Machine Learning

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ABSTRACT

In this report, features of the provided dataset are visualized, where it is analyzed, cleaned using relevant techniques to increase the performance of the algorithm. The “price” feature, which is a continuous target variable, is compared with other features to predict the presales of the “car” while buying or selling.

"I discovered that the informational problems that exist in the used car market were potentially present to some degree in all markets."

-George A. Akerlof, Nobel Prize winner, 2001

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PROBLEM STATEMENT

Buying and Selling used Cars is not as easy a job as compared with buying new ones. In fact, People are not so confident to sell and purchase as they are totally **unaware of the factors** that need to be considered. For sure, they are almost stressed about what **price value** to deal with.

To sort this out to some extent, something is necessary to reduce the asymmetric knowledge gap. For this, a model is created for consumers with some supportive visualizations based on the provided features.

OBJECTIVES

To predict the actual value of the used cars based on the provided information, which helps both buyers and sellers.

Chapter 1: Methodology

Dataset

The dataset contains information about price, transmission, mileage, fuel type, road tax, miles per gallon (mpg), and engine size. As the dataset doesn't include some features like transmission problems, frequent maintenance/servicing, and accident history, the car's event data recorder, and information regarding checks by car Technicians, still, we can still improve the performance more if we gather sufficient data.

Note: Checking mileage rollback on CARFAX is always necessary.

Analysis plan

- Listing and identifying the appropriate performance metrics based on the nature of the problem. Here, "price" is the continuous target variable whose values are to be modeled and predicted by other variables(features). So, to model the relationship between a certain number of features and "price", performance metrics such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Squared Error, Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), and R-Squared are to be used.
- Understanding the relationships between features and developing insights.
- Select an appropriate model, fit it to the data, and validate its results
- Analyze the result.

Performance metrics for Regression

- **Mean Averaged Error**

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |y_i - \hat{y}_i|$$

Fig. 1. Mean Averaged Error

where y_i is the actual expected output and \hat{y}_i is the model's prediction. It is the simplest evaluation metric for a regression scenario and is not as popular compared to the following metrics.

- **Mean Squared Error**

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$$

Fig. 2. Mean Squared Error

Here, the error term is squared and thus **more sensitive to outliers** as compared to Mean Absolute Error (MAE).

- **Root Mean Squared Error**

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n (y_j - \hat{y}_j)^2}$$

Fig. 3. Root Mean Squared Error

Since MSE includes squared error terms, we take the square root of the MSE, which gives rise to Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE).

- **R-squared**

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{SS_{RES}}{SS_{TOT}} = 1 - \frac{\sum_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_i (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

Fig. 4. R-squared

R-squared is calculated by dividing the sum of squares of residuals (**SSres**) from the regression model by the total sum of squares (**SStot**) of errors from the average model and then subtracting it from 1.

Exploratory Data Analysis

1. Loading, inspecting, and handling data.
2. Handling outliers and understanding relationships and new insights through plots.

Loading and inspecting data: Before loading data, import a certain module

```
: import pandas as pd

: import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
```

Fig. 5. Importing libraries

Pandas read_csv() function is used to import a CSV file to the “Sales_data” DataFrame and perform certain operations on it. On inspection, it is seen that the dataframe is of size 6738 rows * 9 columns. Features are model, year, price, transmission, mileage, fuelType, tax, mpg, and engineSize, where “price” is a continuous target variable.

```
data = pd.read_csv('data/toyota.csv')
data
```

	model	year	price	transmission	mileage	fuelType	tax	mpg	engineSize
0	GT86	2016	16000	Manual	24089	Petrol	265	36.2	2.0
1	GT86	2017	15995	Manual	18615	Petrol	145	36.2	2.0
2	GT86	2015	13998	Manual	27469	Petrol	265	36.2	2.0
3	GT86	2017	18998	Manual	14736	Petrol	150	36.2	2.0
4	GT86	2017	17498	Manual	36284	Petrol	145	36.2	2.0
...
6733	IQ	2011	5500	Automatic	30000	Petrol	20	58.9	1.0
6734	Urban Cruiser	2011	4985	Manual	36154	Petrol	125	50.4	1.3
6735	Urban Cruiser	2012	4995	Manual	46000	Diesel	125	57.6	1.4
6736	Urban Cruiser	2011	3995	Manual	60700	Petrol	125	50.4	1.3
6737	Urban Cruiser	2011	4495	Manual	45128	Petrol	125	50.4	1.3

6738 rows × 9 columns

Fig. 6. Exploring Dataframe

Now, Let's check the datatypes and see if there are any missing values.

```
<class 'pandas.core.frame.DataFrame'>
RangeIndex: 6738 entries, 0 to 6737
Data columns (total 9 columns):
#   Column          Non-Null Count  Dtype
---  -
0   model           6738 non-null   object
1   year            6738 non-null   int64
2   price           6738 non-null   int64
3   transmission    6738 non-null   object
4   mileage         6738 non-null   int64
5   fuelType       6738 non-null   object
6   tax             6738 non-null   int64
7   mpg            6738 non-null   float64
8   engineSize     6738 non-null   float64
dtypes: float64(2), int64(4), object(3)
memory usage: 473.9+ KB
```

Since all features, which are either numeric or object data types, have non-null entries, there are no missing values. Great! But, wait. Have to check if there are any of the features having either 0's repeatedly or very few data npoints ot enough to help us in predicting. Also, it's worth it to check whether categories of every feature are very few in number or not.

Let's see summary statistics.

	year	price	mileage	tax	mpg	engineSize
count	6738.000000	6738.000000	6738.000000	6738.000000	6738.000000	6738.000000
mean	2016.748145	12522.391066	22857.413921	94.697240	63.042223	1.471297
std	2.204062	6345.017587	19125.464147	73.880776	15.836710	0.436159
min	1998.000000	850.000000	2.000000	0.000000	2.800000	0.000000
25%	2016.000000	8290.000000	9446.000000	0.000000	55.400000	1.000000
50%	2017.000000	10795.000000	18513.000000	135.000000	62.800000	1.500000
75%	2018.000000	14995.000000	31063.750000	145.000000	69.000000	1.800000
max	2020.000000	59995.000000	174419.000000	565.000000	235.000000	4.500000

From the above table, we see that, average price of a car in this dataset is around 12523, with a minimum price being 850 and a maximum being 59995. The tax and engineSize features have values of 0. This is likely due to wrong or missing data.

```
for c in data.columns:
    if(is_numeric_dtype(data[c])):
        k= data[c][data[c]==0].count()
        if(k):
            print(f"{c} has {k} zero values")
        else:
            print(f"{c} has No zero values")
    else:
        for name, count in data.groupby(c)[c].count().iteritems():
            if(c=="fuelType"):
                if(count < 50):
                    print(f"{name} of the {c} feature has {count} data")
            else:
                if(count < 25):
                    print(f"{name} of the {c} feature has {count} data")
```

After exploring the categorical data, it is seen as;

```
Camry of the model feature has 11 data
IQ of the model feature has 8 data
PROACE VERSO of the model feature has 15 data
Supra of the model feature has 12 data
Urban Cruiser of the model feature has 4 data
Verso-S of the model feature has 3 data
year has No zero values
price has No zero values
Other of the transmission feature has 1 data
mileage has No zero values
tax has 1790 zero values
mpg has No zero values
engineSize has 6 zero values
```

In the above figure, we will work on the actual dataset to remove zero values and less important features.

Data Visualization:

Calculating the total number of each type of fuel to determine which sells at a higher price.

Finding the relationship between the logarithm of the price and both year and mileage.

Clearly, plots below show the linear relationship between the logarithm of the price and both year and mileage. Based on these plots, going forward in the analysis, the log value of price instead of price is supposed to be used.

Finding the relationship between the logarithm of the price and both fuelType and transmission.

With regards to the above plot, it is seen that there are many users who prefer to use diesel and petrol cars over hybrid cars, electric, and “other” cars.. The distribution of prices over the different fuel types appears to be fairly regular and somewhat close to normal distributions. Compared to fuel type categories, the numbers in the transmission categories appear more evenly distributed. From the distributions, it seems that semi-auto cars and automatics are more expensive as compared to others.s.

Counting different types of Car models

The distribution of most of the models shows a one- or two-peak structure, with various mean values, which should make it possible for a linear model to somewhat distinguish between them.

Visualizing the number of car sales and their amount with a histogram

With regards to histogram distribution, it can be noted that around 2,000 cars are sold at a price of around 30k to 1 lakh. Below the price of around 2,800 and above 1 lakh, there are no sales.

Mileage vs Price plot: Less the mileage the higher the cost

Mileage vs price vs year

The yellow colour, referring to 2020 A.D., on the baseline of the Y-axis indicates how pricing changes with a difference in mileage. In 2000 A.D., Cars having 1 lakh mileage cost around 5k, but in 2015, the price increased a little bit more, sharing around the same mileage, as clearly shown in the figure. However, we cannot deny the fact that, lower the mileage of a used car, the higher the price it costs.

HeatMap

In the above figure, it is seen that the price variable has a decent correlation with the other quantitative variables shown above.

At what age do we see a significant drop in car prices?

Log value of price vs model plot

Which models are of the best value?

From the figure, it's clear that it is good to select a car with low cost and low mileage. So, cars belonging to cluster no 4, will be the best buy in terms of mileage and price.

Data Cleaning

```
#price depends upon year, somehow on tax but not mpg and mileage
remove_columns = (data.engineSize == 0) | (data.tax == 0) | (data.model == "IQ") | (data.model == "PROACE VERSO") | (data.model == "Other")
data1 = data.copy(deep = True)
data1 = data1[~remove_columns]
data1
```

```
Camry of the model feature has 11 data
IQ of the model feature has 8 data
PROACE VERSO of the model feature has 15 data
Supra of the model feature has 12 data
Urban Cruiser of the model feature has 4 data
Verso-S of the model feature has 3 data
year has No zero values
price has No zero values
Other of the transmission feature has 1 data
mileage has No zero values
tax has 1790 zero values
mpg has No zero values
engineSize has 6 zero values
```

As shown above, the "Other" category of the fuelType feature is very less in number. So, it's better to drop this as it will not be able to help us predict for those categories. Also, while visualizing, it was seen that these are less important features

CHAPTER 2. Model: Regression

```
#Model
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split, cross_validate
from sklearn.metrics import r2_score
data2_train, data2_val = train_test_split(data2, test_size = 0.33, random_state = 42)
```

Here, 33% percent of the data is held for validation before training any model. Below I a pipeline is build to apply one-hot encoding to all categorical variables in the dataset, before passing the data on to a linear regression.

```
#Using OneHotEncoder to deal with the categorical values and using linear regression as "price" will be
import sklearn
from sklearn.pipeline import Pipeline
from sklearn.preprocessing import OneHotEncoder
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeRegressor
from sklearn.compose import make_column_selector, make_column_transformer

def oneHotFunction(drop= "first"):
    tuplevariable = (OneHotEncoder(drop=drop), make_column_selector(dtype_include = "object"))
    ohe = make_column_transformer(tuplevariable, remainder = "passthrough")
    return ohe
def Linear_OneHotFunction(drop= "first"):
    lr = Pipeline((
        ("one_hot", oneHotFunction(drop=drop)),
        ("regressor",LinearRegression())
    ))
    return lr|
lr = Linear_OneHotFunction()
```

In the above, one-hot encoding is preferred to use to deal with the categorical variables in the data. The linear regression is only able to deal with numerical variables, so to treat categorical variables where there is no numerical relation between the categories, one-hot encoding creates new features for every category, where the value in each of the new features is one for records with that category, but zero otherwise.

Then, log price, engineSize, transmission, mileage, year features with cross-validation are used in the model. This splits the data into five blocks, trains on the first four blocks combined, and tests against the last block. This is repeated 4 times, where each time a new block is used for testing, and the remaining blocks are used for training. This helps check that the score is not artificially high or low due to some particular test/train split.

```
def split(data, dependent = "log price"):
    features = [f for f in data.columns if f != dependent]
    return data[features], data[dependent]
X, y = split(data2_train[["log price", "year"]], dependent = "log price")
score = cross_validate(lr, X, y, return_train_score = True)
pd.DataFrame(score)[["test_score", "train_score"]]
```

	test_score	train_score
0	0.355478	0.278924
1	0.227772	0.309690
2	0.285725	0.297654
3	0.269978	0.301843
4	0.318964	0.289115

Now the following functions are used to add more features one by one to get a better score, and the cross-validation scores of the resulting models is to be compared.

```
col = data2.columns
col
```

```
Index(['model', 'year', 'transmission', 'mileage', 'fuelType', 'tax', 'mpg',
      'engineSize', 'log price'],
      dtype='object')
```

```
data2_reduced = data2[col]
data2_train_reduced = data2_train[col]
data2_val_reduced = data2_val[col]
```

Lasso and Ridge

The training and test scores of the fitted linear model are not very different, which indicates that the model is not overfitting much. This is also expected for linear models, since these models tend to have large bias, but low variance.

To make sure that the data has not been overfit, I performed lasso and ridge regressions for a series of values of their alpha parameters

```
def run_gridsearchcv(model, data, values):
    param_grid = {"regressor__alpha": values}
    clf = GridSearchCV(estimator=model, param_grid=param_grid, return_train_score=True)
    X, y = split_dependent(data, dependent="log price")
    clf.fit(X, y)
    print_cols = [
        "param_regressor__alpha",
        "mean_test_score",
        "mean_train_score",
        "std_test_score",
        "std_train_score",
    ]
    display(
        pd.DataFrame(clf.cv_results_)[print_cols].set_index("param_regressor__alpha")
    )

lasso = Pipeline(("one_hot", make_cat_ohc()), ("regressor", Lasso()))
run_gridsearchcv(lasso, Sales_Data_for_model_reduced, [0.0005, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1])
```

	mean_test_score	mean_train_score	std_test_score	std_train_score
param_regressor__alpha				
0.0005	0.871174	0.899745	0.024042	0.006787
0.0010	0.848601	0.881242	0.029324	0.008194
0.0100	0.780284	0.824805	0.040142	0.016537
0.1000	0.433776	0.541185	0.074266	0.025313

```
ridge = Pipeline(("one_hot", make_cat_ohc()), ("regressor", Ridge(tol=1e-9)))
run_gridsearchcv(ridge, Sales_Data_for_model_reduced, [0] + list(10 ** i for i in range(5)))
```

	mean_test_score	mean_train_score	std_test_score	std_train_score
param_regressor__alpha				
0	0.905778	0.927010	0.019550	0.004597
1	0.905520	0.926823	0.019493	0.004605
10	0.897339	0.920619	0.020196	0.005038
100	0.860336	0.890855	0.026404	0.007889
1000	0.811522	0.850454	0.035370	0.012529
10000	0.639956	0.711396	0.055769	0.025442

```
X, y = split_dependent(Sales_Data_for_model_train_reduced, dependent="log price")
linreg.fit(X, y)
X_val, y_val = split_dependent(Sales_Data_for_model_val_reduced, dependent="log price")
y_predict_val = linreg.predict(X_val)
data_score = r2_score(y_val, y_predict_val)
data_score
```

0.9304659838309818

```

def eval_model(models, **kwargs):
    features = find_longest_element(list(models.keys()))
    # print(features)
    for key in kwargs:
        if key not in features:
            raise ValueError(f"{key} not found in {features}")
    chosen_features = tuple(feature for feature in features if feature in kwargs)
    model_holder = models[chosen_features]
    model = model_holder["model"]
    dy = model_holder["dy_90"]

    values = (scalar_to_list(kwargs[feature]) for feature in chosen_features)
    X = pd.DataFrame(
        dict(
            zip(
                chosen_features,
                values,
            )
        )
    )

```

#Predicting price

```

def find_largest_element(keys):
    return keys[np.argmax(list(map(len, keys)))]

def scalar_to_list(x):
    if(np.isscalar(x)):
        return [x]
    else:
        return x

def predict(models, **kwargs):
    features = find_largest_element(list(models.keys()))
    provided_features = tuple(f for f in features if f in kwargs)
    model_holder = models[provided_features]
    model = model_holder["model"]
    values = (scalar_to_list(kwargs[f]) for f in provided_features)
    X = pd.DataFrame(
        dict (
            zip(
                provided_features, values
            )
        )
    )
    predicted_price = pd.DataFrame({
        "model": X["model"], "transmission": X["transmission"], "price": np.power(10, model.predict(X))
    })
    return predicted_price

def powerset(features, start = 0):
    return chain.from_iterable(combinations(list(features),r) for r in range(start, len(list(features)) +1))

def training_features(features, data, dependent = "log price"):
    models = {}
    for f in powerset(features, start = 1):
        lr = Linear_OneHotFunction()
        x = data[list(f)]
        y = data[dependent]
        lr.fit(x,y)
        models[f] = {"model": lr}
    return models

```

```
predicted_price= predict(models, model = 2*[" GT86"], transmission=["Manual", "Automatic"])
predicted_price
```

```

|:  model transmission  price
|:  ---
0   GT86      Manual  18402.562145
1   GT86      Automatic 24698.113776

```

In the predict function, it takes keyword arguments and returns a pandas dataframe with the predicted price. So, we can conclude that price depends upon the factors model, mileage, and year very much. The predicted price is solely dependent on those factors.

```

from sklearn import metrics
y_test = results['actual']
y_pred = results['predicted']

print('Mean Absolute Error:', metrics.mean_absolute_error(y_test, y_pred))
print('Mean Squared Error:', metrics.mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred))
print('Root Mean Squared Error:', np.sqrt(metrics.mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred)))

```

```

Mean Absolute Error: 0.043489863791363326
Mean Squared Error: 0.0035158471257730347
Root Mean Squared Error: 0.05929457922755701

```

```

predict_lr = lr.predict(x_test)
print('real value y_test[1]:'+str(y_test[1])+ ' predict:'+str(lr.predict(x_test.iloc[[1],:]))
print('score:',lr.score(x_test,y_test))
print('r2 score:',r2_score(y_test,predict_lr))
print("Training MSE:",np.sqrt(mse(y_train,lr.predict(x_train))))
print("Testing MSE:",np.sqrt(mse(y_test,lr.predict(x_test))))
print("Training R2_score:",r2_score(y_train,lr.predict(x_train)))
print("Testing R2_score:",r2_score(y_test,lr.predict(x_test)))

```

```

real value y_test[1]:4.431363764158987  predict:[4.19406776]
score: 0.9166739722632481
r2 score: 0.916673972263248
Training MSE: 0.05655124867043534
Testing MSE: 0.05929063029173887
Training R2_score: 0.9269296676054011
Testing R2_score: 0.916673972263248

```

```

from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor

rfr = RandomForestRegressor()
rfr.fit(x_train,y_train)
predict_rfr = rfr.predict(x_test)
print('real value y_test[1]:'+str(y_test[1])+ ' predict: '+str(rfr.predict(x_test.iloc[[1],:])))
print('score:',rfr.score(x_test,y_test))
print('r2 score:',r2_score(y_test,predict_rfr))
print('r2 score:',r2_score(y_test,predict_lr))
print("Training MSE:",np.sqrt(mse(y_train,rfr.predict(x_train))))
print("Testing MSE:",np.sqrt(mse(y_test,rfr.predict(x_test))))
print("Training R2_score:",r2_score(y_train,rfr.predict(x_train)))
print("Testing R2_score:",r2_score(y_test,rfr.predict(x_test)))

```

```

real value y_test[1]:4.431363764158987  predict:[4.13821403]
score: 0.9451441069326979
r2 score: 0.945144106932698
r2 score: 0.916673972263248
Training MSE: 0.017089451002674436
Testing MSE: 0.048106900076051194
Training R2_score: 0.993327126251841
Testing R2_score: 0.945144106932698

```

```

y_test = results['actual']
y_pred = results['predicted']

print('Mean Absolute Error:', metrics.mean_absolute_error(y_test, y_pred))
print('Mean Squared Error:', metrics.mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred))
print('Root Mean Squared Error:', np.sqrt(metrics.mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred)))

```

```

Mean Absolute Error: 0.031770730041905365
Mean Squared Error: 0.002314997692429057
Root Mean Squared Error: 0.048114422914850144

```

```

from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeRegressor

dtr = DecisionTreeRegressor()
dtr.fit(x_train,y_train)
predict_dtr = dtr.predict(x_test)
print('real value y_test[1]:'+str(y_test[1])+ ' predict: '+str(dtr.predict(x_test.iloc[[1],:])))
print('score:',dtr.score(x_test,y_test))
print('r2 score:',r2_score(y_test,predict_dtr))
print('r2 score:',r2_score(y_test,predict_lr))
print("Training MSE:",np.sqrt(mse(y_train,dtr.predict(x_train))))
print("Testing MSE:",np.sqrt(mse(y_test,dtr.predict(x_test))))
print("Training R2_score:",r2_score(y_train,dtr.predict(x_train)))
print("Testing R2_score:",r2_score(y_test,dtr.predict(x_test)))

```

```

real value y_test[1]:4.431363764158987  predict:[4.18892848]
score: 0.9075538638884907
r2 score: 0.9075538638884908
r2 score: 0.916673972263248
Training MSE: 0.003537840123997175
Testing MSE: 0.062451102499152394
Training R2_score: 0.9997140216923882
Testing R2_score: 0.9075538638884908

```

```

#LinearRegression
from sklearn.pipeline import Pipeline

def Linear_OneHotEncoder(drop="first"):
    Linear_OneHot = Pipeline((
        ("one_hot", oneHotFunction(drop=drop)),
        ("regressor", LinearRegression()),
    ))
    return Linear_OneHot

linear_oneHot = Linear_OneHotEncoder()
x, y = split(data2_train_reduced, dependent = "log price")
linear_oneHot.fit(x,y)
x_val, y_val = split(data2_val_reduced, dependent = "log price")
y_val_predict = linear_oneHot.predict(x_val)
L = r2_score(y_val, y_val_predict)
L

```

: 0.9542537954150673

```

#DecisionTree
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeRegressor

def DecisionTree_OneHotEncoder(drop="first"):
    DecisionTree_OneHot = Pipeline((
        ("one_hot", oneHotFunction(drop=drop)),
        ("regressor", DecisionTreeRegressor()),
    ))
    return DecisionTree_OneHot

DecisionTree_OneHot = DecisionTree_OneHotEncoder()
x, y = split(data2_train_reduced, dependent = "log price")
DecisionTree_OneHot.fit(x,y)
x_val, y_val = split(data2_val_reduced, dependent = "log price")
y_val_predict = DecisionTree_OneHot.predict(x_val)
D = r2_score(y_val, y_val_predict)
D

```

: 0.9280210162680768

```

#RandomForest
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor

def RandomForest_OneHotEncoder(drop="first"):
    RandomForest_OneHot = Pipeline((
        ("one_hot", oneHotFunction(drop=drop)),
        ("regressor", RandomForestRegressor()),
    ))
    return RandomForest_OneHot

RandomForest_OneHot = RandomForest_OneHotEncoder()
x, y = split(data2_train_reduced, dependent = "log price")
RandomForest_OneHot.fit(x,y)
x_val, y_val = split(data2_val_reduced, dependent = "log price")
y_val_predict = RandomForest_OneHot.predict(x_val)
R = r2_score(y_val, y_val_predict)
R

```

: 0.9549480667257688

```
1: y = np.array([L,D,R])
   x = ["LinearRegression", "DecisionTree", "RandomForest"]
   plt.bar(x,y)
   plt.xlabel('Regressor')
   plt.ylabel('r2 score')
   #plt.xticks(rotation = 90)
   plt.show()
```


Conclusion

The goal of this project was to make a regression model for predicting the resale prices of cars. Based on the details of the available data, a linear model was chosen to fit the data. Upon performing feature selection, it appeared that the year, mileage, and model features influence the price a lot. The engine size and transmission features had a smaller influence on the price. Finally, the fuelType, mpg, and tax features did not seem to have any influence on the price within the linear model, so these features were not included in the final model, which contained the other 5 features.

Comparisons of R^2 train and test scores, as well as lasso and ridge regularizers, indicated that the model was not overfitting. The feature selected model has an R^2 score of 0.95 when tested on the validation set, so the model seems to be fairly accurate. When compared to different regression models, it is obtained that LinearRegression and RandomForest lead the DecisionTree Regressor.

Finally, different performance metrics were calculated on different models, like linear, random forest, and decision tree, and an R^2 value of above 0.9% was predicted as shown in the figure.

The data had some issues, most notably in the mpg, tax, and engineSize variables, which contained some suspicious values. Also, I would have expected that the MPG and tax features should be predictable from the car model and related info, but this did not appear to be the case. The dataset contains information about price, transmission, mileage, fuel type, road tax, miles per gallon (mpg), and engine size. As the dataset doesn't include some features like transmission problems, frequent maintenance/servicing, and accident history, the car's event data recorder, and information regarding checks by car Technicians, still, we can still improve the performance more if we gather sufficient data. Checking mileage rollback on CARFAX is always necessary.